

IMPACT OF MONETARY AND FISCAL POLICIES ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN RESOURCE-BASED COUNTRIES: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN NIGERIA AND LIBYA

Oreitan Adigun^{1*}, Oluwatoyin A. Matthew²

¹ The Chartered Institute of Bankers of Nigeria, Victoria Island, Lagos, Nigeria. oreitanadigun@gmail.com

² Department of Economics and Development Studies, Covenant University, Ota, Nigeria.
oluwatoyin.matthew@covenantuniversity.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18049713>

Abstract

Resource-based economies are countries whose Gross Domestic Product (GDP) to a large extent comes from natural resources, of which Nigeria and Libya fall into this category. The impact of monetary and fiscal policies on the economic growth of these countries cannot be overemphasized. It is against this backdrop that this study examined the comparative analysis of the impact of monetary and fiscal policies on economic growth in Nigeria and Libya, using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and the Granger causality test. The secondary data used in this study were obtained from the World Development Indicators (WDI), spanning the period from 1990 to 2023. The results of this study showed that the error correction term for Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) is negative and significant, confirming the long-run equilibrium adjustment. In the short run, government expenditure, government revenue, and inflation significantly influence RGDP, while labour force participation and exchange rate show weaker effects. Therefore, this study recommended that expansionary fiscal policy should be embarked upon in the long-run as this will help boost economic growth in both countries.

Keywords: Fiscal Policy, Economic Growth, Monetary Policy, Resource-based, VECM

1. INTRODUCTION

Resource-based economies are countries whose Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and revenue generated come mainly from natural resources. These resources can be classified into the following categories viz; renewable resources, examples are solar energy, wind energy and hydroelectric power; and non-renewable resources, for example, coal, natural gas and crude oil; biotic resources, for example, forests, animals and marine life; abiotic resources such as minerals like iron and gold, and resources like air and water. Natural resources are fundamental for human survival, providing essential elements like food, water, air, and shelter, while also driving economic growth and supporting various industries. They are crucial for maintaining ecosystems, offering habitats for wildlife, and contributing to climate regulation. However, their finite nature necessitates responsible management and conservation to ensure their availability for future generations (Kerner et al., 2023; Banjo et al., 2024).

Monetary policy influences the level of money stock and/or interest rate, that is, availability, value, and cost of credit in consonance with the level of economic activity. Macroeconomic aggregates such as output, employment, and prices are, in turn, affected by the stance of monetary policy through several ways, including interest rate or money, credit, wealth or portfolio, and exchange rate channels (Njeze, 2023; Hakimah, 2025). The monetary authorities apply discretionary power to influence the money stock and interest rate to make money either more expensive or cheaper, depending on the prevailing economic conditions and policy stance, to achieve price stability. This is why Tajudeen and Adesina, (2024), concluded that monetary policy is nothing but a deliberate attempt to control the money supply and credit conditions to achieve certain broad economic objectives. In general, monetary authorities or Central Banks

are saddled with controlling inflation, maintaining a healthy balance of payments position to safeguard the external value of the domestic currency, and promoting economic growth (Olapade 2025; Muhammed & Oladipo 2024; Ngaikedi et al., 2023).

Fiscal policy, which involves government spending and taxation, significantly impacts economic growth. It can be used to stimulate growth during recessions by increasing government spending and decreasing taxes, or to curb inflation and stabilize the economy by cutting spending and raising taxes. Fiscal policy can also play a role in long-term development by investing in infrastructure and education. Government spending, a fundamental component of fiscal policy, directly affects economic activity by injecting funds into the economy. Public investments in infrastructure, education, and healthcare can enhance productivity and foster long-term growth. However, the effectiveness of such spending depends on its efficiency and the economic context in which it occurs. For instance, during periods of economic downturn, increased government spending can stimulate demand and mitigate the effects of a recession (Tan et al., 2020). On the other hand, taxation, another crucial element of fiscal policy, influences economic behaviour and resource allocation. Tax policies can either incentivize or discourage investment, consumption, and labour supply. High tax rates may reduce disposable income and dampen economic activity, while well-designed tax incentives can spur innovation and growth. The challenge for policymakers lies in striking a balance between generating sufficient revenue and fostering an environment conducive to economic expansion (Kabashi, 2017).

Economic growth refers to an increase in the production of goods and services in an economy. Increases in capital goods, taxation, labour force, technology, expansionary fiscal policy that increases government expenditure on capital projects, monetary policy instruments, and human capital can all contribute to economic growth. In the light of the importance of monetary and fiscal policies to boost economic growth, this study sets out to examine the impact of monetary and fiscal policies on economic growth in resource-based countries, doing a comparative analysis of Nigeria and Libya. The choice of Nigeria and Libya stems from the fact that both countries are endowed with many natural resources, especially oil, and have carried out monetary and fiscal policies' reforms from the 1990s to date. The study period spans between 1990 and 2023, this emphasis on this period is because it witnessed a lot of monetary and fiscal policies' reforms in Nigeria and Libya. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, this study is one of the few studies that did a comparative study of two or more countries, and focused on both monetary and fiscal policies at the same time. Other previous studies (Njeze 2023; Muhammed & Oladipo 2024; Khan et al. 2025; Pastpipatkul & Ko 2025) in the literature focused on either monetary policy or fiscal policy individually, and carried out country specific study. Thus, this study intends to fill the research gap in these areas.

The study formulated and tested two hypotheses: (1) H_0 : monetary and fiscal policies do not have a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria; and (2) H_0 : monetary and fiscal policies do not have a significant effect on economic growth in Libya. The remaining part of the paper is divided into four sections. Following the introduction is the literature review in Section 2, the methodology employed is discussed in Section 3, the analysis is presented in Section 4, the results of the study are discussed in Section 5, conclusion and policy implications are presented in Section 6, while limitations and further studies are presented in Section 7.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Njeze, (2023), monetary policy is a set of actions to used to control a country's overall money supply and achieve exchange rate stability, stable prices, and a forward balance of payment. According to Muhammed and Oladipo, (2024), monetary policy strategies include revising interest rates and changing bank reserve requirements. Monetary policy is commonly classified as either expansionary or

contractionary. Monetary policy is one of the two principal means (the other being fiscal policy) by which government authorities in a market economy regularly influence the pace and direction of overall economic activity, importantly not only the level of aggregate output and employment but also the general rate at which prices rise or fall (Şahin, 2025).

Tajudeen and Adesina, (2024), observed that the government usually uses monetary policy, typically via the apex bank in the country called Central Bank, by exploring their control over the supply of certain kinds of claims against the Central Bank hence the label “monetary” that enables a country's businesses, banks, and individuals to carry out their day-to-day economic activities. Olawale (2024), defined monetary policy as the actions of the Central Bank to regulate the money supply, to achieve the ultimate macroeconomic objectives of government. In most financial systems, banks are legally required to hold claims against the Central Bank to create deposits and make loans, and so the Central Bank's control over the supply of claims against itself also gives it a form of control over the economy's money and credit in a far broader sense. The evidence from experience, in one country after another, makes clear that exercising this control monetary policy powerfully affects a country's economic growth, either positively or negatively (Obradović & Grubišić, 2025).

Amidu et al., (2022), opined that monetary policy affects the economy by changing the supply of money and the availability of credit. The tools of monetary policy affect the way banks use their reserves of money deposited into checking, savings, and other accounts to make loans to consumers and businesses. The authors opined that monetary policy refers to the actions taken by a Central Bank or monetary authority to manage the supply of money and interest rates in an economy, with the aim of promoting economic growth and stability. To affect the price and accessibility of credit, this may entail altering the money supply, setting interest rates, or utilizing other instruments.

According to Ngaikedi et al., (2023), the chief objectives of monetary policy in modern times have typically been to maintain the stability of a country's general price level, that is, to prevent either inflation or deflation; and to promote maximum levels of output and employment. Other often accepted goals of monetary policy include maintaining balance in a country's international trade, preserving stability in its financial markets, and fostering increased capital investment to enhance its economic growth over time. Apart from preserving financial market stability, which is usually taken to be secondary, all these objectives pertain to aspects of an economy's non-financial economic activity.

Fiscal policy, on the other hand, has a significant impact on economic growth via influencing aggregate demand, employment, and investment through government spending and taxation. Changes in government spending and tax revenue can stimulate or dampen economic activity in the short run but in the long run, fiscal policy can promote economic growth through investment in human capital and infrastructure. Government spending, a fundamental component of fiscal policy, directly affects economic activity by injecting funds into the economy. Public investments in infrastructure, education, and healthcare can enhance productivity and foster long-term growth (Khan et al., 2025).

However, the effectiveness of such spending depends on its efficiency and the economic context in which it occurs. For instance, during periods of economic downturn, increased government spending can stimulate demand and mitigate the effects of a recession (Tan et al., 2020; Utouh & Kitole, 2025). On the other hand,

taxation, another crucial element of fiscal policy, influences economic behaviour and resource allocation. Tax policies can either incentivize or discourage investment, consumption, and labour supply. High tax rates may reduce disposable income and dampen economic activity, while well-designed tax incentives can spur innovation and economic growth. The challenge for policymakers lies in striking a balance between generating sufficient revenue and fostering an environment conducive to economic expansion (Kabashi, 2017). The relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth is also mediated by the fiscal multiplier, a measure of the impact of fiscal interventions on economic output. A high fiscal multiplier suggests that government spending or tax cuts have a significant positive effect on GDP, whereas a low multiplier indicates a more muted response. Factors such as the state of the economy, the type of fiscal measures, and the level of public debt influence the magnitude of the fiscal multiplier (Gaber et al., 2023; Pastpipatkul & Ko, 2025).

The theoretical premise of this study is hinged on the “bi-directional causality” otherwise known as the “feedback hypothesis” propounded by Patrick in 1966, he ascribes equal importance to both the financial and real sectors of the economy since it assumes a positive two-way causal relationship between finance and growth. This view postulates that the causal link between financial development and economic growth alternates as the economy develops. In the early stage, the supply-leading process holds and as the economy grows, it fades away and demand-following prevails (Amidu et al., 2022; Muhammed & Oladipo, 2024). Patrick's feedback hypothesis, also known as the "stage-of-development hypothesis", suggests a two-way relationship between financial development and economic growth. It proposes that financial development can both lead and follow economic growth, meaning that the financial system can drive economic expansion, and conversely, economic growth can also stimulate the financial sector. Since monetary and fiscal policies are embedded in the financial domain, this means that they can both stimulate economic growth.

2.1 An Overview of the Nigerian and Libyan Economies

Nigeria is a country that is blessed with so many natural resources and a large market size in terms of population. In 1990, government expenditure in Nigeria was about US\$7.8 billion and rose to about US\$37.6 billion in 2023 (Saheb, Sidaoui & Schmarzo, 2024). When this is compared to Libya, which has the same pre-historical background (in terms of having so many natural resources but with a smaller population than Nigeria), government expenditure was about US\$5.8 billion and rose to US\$15.9 billion in 2023. In terms of government revenue, Nigeria's revenue was about US\$12.6 billion in 1990 and rose to US\$27.2 billion in 2023. While Libya's revenue rose to US\$22.1 billion in 2023 from US\$6.4 billion. It is evident from these figures that Nigeria had a budget surplus in 1990 and a budget deficit in 2023, while Libya had a budget surplus in 1990 and in 2023. Since the millennium started, Nigeria has been battling with the issues of terrorism and insecurity, which have affected so many sectors of the economy – agriculture, tourism, industry, education, and so on. These problems have greatly affected the revenue-generating capacity of the country. As it stands presently, Nigeria borrows to finance part of its annual budget (World Bank, 2024).

In terms of the monetary policies, the inflation rate in Nigeria was about 7.36% in 1990 and rose to 28.92% in 2023. While in Libya, the inflation rate was about 5.4% in 1990 and fell to 2.37% in 2023. In 1990, Nigeria's nominal savings and maximum lending rates were 18.8% and 27.7% respectively while in 2023

both fell to 15% and 18.75% respectively. In Libya, nominal savings and maximum lending rates were 9.8% and 17.7% in 1990; both fell to 7.75% and 11.65% in 2023. In Nigeria, the exchange rate of the Naira to the US Dollar was 460.702 in 2023 from 50.671 in 1990. This shows a great devaluation in the value of the Nigerian currency. The Libyan statistics show that the exchange rate of the Dinar (Libya's currency) to the US Dollar was 76.4 in 2023 from 17.01 in 1990. This shows that the value of the Libyan currency to the US Dollar is greater than the Nigerian currency (World Bank, 2024).

The post-COVID-19 era has witnessed the 'JAPA' syndrome, a term used to describe the relocation of professional workers from both the Nigerian and Libyan economies in search of greener pastures in developed countries such as Canada, the United States of America, France, Germany, the United Kingdom, and so on. Nigeria's situation seems to be worse since there is a high level of insecurity and an increase in the inflation rate, coupled with the poor remuneration paid to workers in the country. This has affected the health, education, and IT-related sectors negatively, as there is a dearth of such professionals in Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Model Specification

The model for this study established the relationship between monetary policy, fiscal policy, and economic growth in Nigeria and Libya. The model is adapted from the study by Matthew et al. (2019), which examined the relationship among technology-based foreign direct investment, manufacturing output, and economic growth in Nigeria and Malaysia.

$$RGDPG_{NIG} = f(GEXP_{NIG}, GREV_{NIG}, INFR_{NIG}, REER_{NIG}, LFPR_{NIG}) \quad (1a)$$

$$RGDPG_{MAL} = f(GEXPLIB, GREV_{LIB}, INFR_{LIB}, REER_{LIB}, LFPR_{LIB}) \quad (1b)$$

Where: f is a functional relationship, $RGDP$ represents the real gross domestic product; $GEXP$ represents gross national expenditure; $GREV$ represents the net national revenue; $INFR$ represents inflation rate, $REER$ represents real effective exchange rate; $LFPR$ represents labour force participation rate; while NIG and LIB represents Nigeria and Libya respectively. Given the above, the equations for Nigeria and Libya.

Equations 1a and 1b are specified in econometric forms as shown in equations 2a and 2b.

$$RGDPG_{NIG} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GEXP_{NIG(t)} + \beta_2 GREV_{NIG(t)} + \beta_3 INFR_{NIG(t)} + \beta_4 REER_{NIG(t)} + \beta_5 LFPR_{NIG(t)} + \mu_t \quad (2a)$$

$$RGDPG_{LIB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GEXPLIB(t) + \beta_2 GREV_{LIB(t)} + \beta_3 INFR_{LIB(t)} + \beta_4 REER_{LIB(t)} + \beta_5 LFPR_{LIB(t)} + \mu_t \quad (2b)$$

Where: β_0 is the intercept term, β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , and β_4 are coefficients of the explanatory variables, μ represents the error term (which is assumed to be normally distributed with a mean of 0 and constant variance). The *a priori* expectations for the variables are stated in such a way that the likely signs of the parameter in line with the empirical evidence are depicted such that: $\beta_1 > 0$, $\beta_2 > 0$, $\beta_3 < 0$, $\beta_4 < 0$, $\beta_5 > 0$. The coefficient of $GEXP(\beta_1)$ is expected to be positive. This implies that an increase in government expenditure will lead to a rise in the GDP growth rate. The coefficient of $GREV(\beta_2)$ is expected to be positive; this means that a rise in government revenue will lead to a rise in the economic growth rate. The coefficient of $INFR(\beta_3)$ is expected to be negative. This is because the higher the inflation rate, the less impact it will have on the growth of the economy. The coefficient of $REER(\beta_4)$ is also expected to be negative, such that a rise in the exchange rate, a lower growth

rate. This is because investors will not be encouraged to invest in such a country. The coefficient of LFPR (β_5) is expected to be positive. This implies that an increase in the labour participation rate will lead to a rise in the GDP growth rate.

3.2 Technique of Estimation

Evaluating empirically a time series data on the effect of monetary and fiscal policies on economic growth of Nigeria and Libya, the unit root test was conducted to determine the trend of the variables. The unit root test is performed to test for stationarity in a time series data. To test for unit root or stationarity at level and first difference, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and the Phillip Perron test was adopted. After the unit root test, this study employed the Vector Error Correction model (VECM) because the variables were observed to be integrated at order 1 [1(1)]. The VECM is an econometric tool that captures both short-term fluctuations and long-term equilibrium relationships among macroeconomic variables. The strength of this model lies in flexibility with integration orders, short-and long-term analysis, and simplicity in implementation.

3.3 Description, Sources and Measurement of Variables

Table 1: Description, Sources and Measurement of Variables

Variable Name & Identifier	Definition	Measurement	Source
Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP)	This refers to the annual percentage change in the value of the final goods and services produced in a country within a year. This is the proxy for economic growth.	Percentage	World Development Indicators, 2024
Gross National Expenditure (GEXP)	This refers to the total government expenditure on the various sectors. This is used to proxy fiscal policy.	US Dollars	WDI, 2024
Net National Revenue (GREV)	This refers to the total revenue made by the government from all sources. This is a proxy for fiscal policy.	US Dollars	WDI, 2024
Inflation rate (INFR)	This refers to the percentage increase in the price of goods and services over a specific period, usually a year. It reflects how quickly the purchasing power of money is decreasing. This is used to proxy monetary policy.	Percentage	WDI, 2024
Real effective exchange rate (REER)	This refers to the weighted average of a country's currency in relation to an index or basket of other major currencies. The weights are determined by comparing the relative trade balance of a country's currency against each country within the index. This is a proxy for fiscal policy.	Index	WDI, 2023

Labour force participation rate (LFPR)	This refers to the percentage of the working age population that is employed. This is used as a control variable.	Percentage	WDI, 2023
--	---	------------	-----------

Source: Researchers' Compilation, 2025.

4. ANALYSIS

1.1 4.1 Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Table 2: Summary Statistics for Nigeria

	GEXP	GREV	INFR	LFPR	REER	RGDP
Mean	137.3880	206.1947	18.27805	55.54129	109.5048	322.7849
Median	25.87682	213.2117	12.94178	56.58350	100.5682	300.1515
Maximum	872.3526	483.5902	72.83550	65.02100	273.0147	550.6477
Minimum	1.320737	18.50178	5.388008	41.98600	49.77717	153.1788
Std. Dev.	212.7075	155.0141	15.90202	7.182255	48.08933	146.4667

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews 9, 2025.

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables us for Nigeria in the study. The results showed that the net national revenue (GREV) has a minimum value of N18.50billion and a maximum value of N483.59billion. On average, the net national revenue (GREV) is N206.19billion with a standard deviation of N155.01billion. GDP constant 2015 US\$ (RGDP) averages \$322.78 billion, with a wide range from \$153.18billion to \$550.65billion, showing significant economic size changes, with a standard deviation of \$146.47billion showing a moderate variation. Gross National Expenditure (GEXP) has the highest spread of N212.71billion, which suggests periods of unusually high spending, and averaging N137.39billion, reaching a maximum of N872.35billion. Inflation rate proxied by the consumer price index (INFR) averages 18.28%, but is highly volatile, judging from the standard deviation of 15.9%, reaching as high as 72.84%, indicating major instability in price levels. Labour participation rates exhibit some variability, ranging from 41.99% to 65.02%. The standard deviation of 7.18% suggests a moderate spread, around the mean of 55.54%, and a median value of 56.58% which is slightly higher than the mean. Finally, the Real effective exchange rate (REER) has an average of 109.5, fluctuating between 49.78 and 273.01, with a standard deviation of 48.09, reflecting notable volatility in currency strength over the years.

Table 3: Summary Statistics for Libya

	GEXP	GREV	INFR	LFPR	REER	RGDP
Mean	51.37553	35.31685	5.236238	67.17756	116.2855	60.44847
Median	45.33215	33.18740	3.629785	69.57100	105.7383	56.29343
Maximum	182.7216	65.41804	25.85387	79.04400	222.4385	83.91266
Minimum	7.484700	15.47529	-9.797647	45.29300	88.26437	41.67227
Std. Dev.	43.80296	16.94782	7.642395	9.316670	25.32183	11.84003

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

From Table 3, the net national revenue (GREV) ranges from N15.48billion to N65.42billion, on average, (GREV) is N35.32billion, median of N33.19billion, and a standard deviation of N16.95billion. Real Gross Domestic Product at constant 2015 US dollars (RGDP) has a minimum value of \$41.67billion and a maximum of \$83.91billion, median of \$56.29billion and a mean of \$60.45billion and a standard deviation of \$11.84billion. Gross National Expenditure (GEXP) ranges from N7.48billion to N182.72billion, with an average and standard deviation of N51.38billion and

N43.80billion respectively. In addition, inflation, measured by consumer price index (INFR), shows an average of 5.24% with a standard deviation of 7.64%, and ranges from -9.80% to 25.85%. Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR) ranges from 45.29% to 79.04%, with a mean of 67.18%, a median of 69.57% and a standard deviation of 9.32% indicating a moderate spread around the mean. Also, the real effective exchange rate (REER) has an average of 116.29, with minimum and maximum values of 88.26 and 222.44 respectively, and a standard deviation of 25.32, indicating moderate fluctuations in currency competitiveness over the period.

1.2 4.1.1 Stationarity Test: Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) Test Results

Table 4: Stationarity Test of Variables (Nigeria)

	ADF			Phillip Perron		
	Level	First Difference	Decision	Level	First Difference	Decision
GREV	0.7814	0.0127	I (1)	0.8474	0.0248	I (1)
RGDP	0.9614	0.0501	I (1)	0.9841	0.0000	I (1)
GEXP	0.9993	0.0052	I (1)	1.0000	0.0000	I (1)
INFR	0.2175	0.0008	I (1)	0.1338	0.0008	I (1)
LPFR	0.3826	0.0058	I (1)	0.6888	0.0001	I (1)
REER	0.0926	0.0001	I (1)	0.0683	0.0001	I (1)

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

Table 4 summarizes the stationarity results for Nigeria using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests. The p-values indicate that all variables—net national revenue (GREV), real GDP (RGDP), gross national expenditure (GEXP), inflation (INFR), labor force participation rate (LFPR), and real effective exchange rate (REER)—are non-stationary at the level but become stationary at first difference, meaning they are integrated of order one, I(1). This is consistent across both ADF and PP tests, and the results are significant at the 1% and 5% levels.

Table 5: Stationarity Test of Variables (Libya)

	ADF			Phillips Perron		
	Level	First Difference	Decision	Level	First Difference	Decision
GREV	0.4600	0.0001	I (1)	0.4609	0.0000	I (1)
RGDP	0.2505	0.0000	I (1)	0.0859	0.0000	I (1)
GEXP	0.9997	0.0003	I (1)	1.0000	0.0002	I (1)
INFR	0.1400	0.0003	I (1)	0.1713	0.0000	I (1)
LFPR	0.6769	0.0018	I (1)	0.1332	0.0011	I (1)
REER	0.3076	0.0000	I (1)	0.1429	0.0001	I (1)

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

Similarly, Table 5 summarizes the stationarity results for Libya using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests. The tests show that all variables, net national revenue (GREV), real GDP (RGDP), gross national expenditure (GEXP), inflation rate (INFR), labour force participation Rate (LFPR), and real effective exchange rate (REER), are non-stationary at the level and become stationary at first difference. This indicates that these series are also integrated of order one, I (1), and the results are statistically significant at 1% and 5% levels.

4.2 Econometric Analysis Results

4.2.1 Results for Nigeria

Table 6: Co-integration Test Result for Nigeria

Hypothesized	Trace Statistic				Maximum Eigenvalue Statistic			
	No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistics	0.05 Critical Value
None *	0.758	168.188	95.754	0.0000	0.758	45.398	40.077	0.0115
At most 1 *	0.716	122.790	69.819	0.0000	0.716	40.274	33.877	0.0075
At most 2 *	0.626	82.516	47.856	0.0000	0.626	31.477	27.584	0.0150
At most 3 *	0.620	51.038	29.797	0.0001	0.620	30.922	21.132	0.0015
At most 4	0.404	20.117	15.49471	0.0093	0.404	16.584	14.265	0.0211
At most 5	0.105	3.533	3.841	0.0601	0.105	3.533	3.841	0.0601

Trace test indicates 4 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level; Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level; * denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level; **MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

Table 6 reveals the co-integration test result on the relationship between real GDP, government expenditure, government revenue, inflation, real effective exchange rate, and labour force participation in Nigeria. The test statistics indicate that the hypothesis of no cointegration among the variables can be rejected. The trace and maximum eigenvalue statistics both confirm that there are up to five cointegrating relations in the model. The presence of these cointegrating relations is enough to confirm that a long-run equilibrium relationship exists among the variables. This means the study can proceed to estimate the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM).

Table 7: Lag Order Selection Result (Nigeria)

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-900.23	NA	9.93e+17	58.466	58.744	58.557
1	-657.53	375.790	1.68e+12	45.131	47.074*	45.764
2	-611.36	53.617	1.16e+12	44.475	48.083	45.651
3	-538.55	56.369*	2.59e+11*	42.099*	47.373	43.819*

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

Table 7 shows the lag order selection result for Nigeria. The lag order selection criteria show that lag 3 is the most appropriate lag length for the model. This is supported by the sequential modified likelihood ratio (LR) statistic, which is highest at lag 3 (56.369), and by the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Final Prediction Error (FPE), both of which reach their minimum at lag 3, with AIC at 42.099 and FPE at 2.59e+11. Although the Schwarz Information Criterion (SC) suggests lag 1, most of the criteria, including the Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion (HQ), favour lag 3, so this lag length can be selected for estimating the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM).

The results in Appendix I (see the appendices section) present the vector error correction estimates for Nigeria, which examined the relationship between RGDP, government expenditure, government revenue, labour force participation, real effective exchange rate, and inflation. The results show that the error correction term for RGDP is negative and significant, confirming long-run equilibrium adjustment. In the short run, government expenditure, government revenue, and inflation rate significantly influence RGDP, while labour force participation and exchange rate show weaker effects. The model explains about 95% of the variation in RGDP, indicating a strong overall fit.

The highlighted column in Appendix I was therefore interpreted and broken down in Table 8. The results reveal the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) result of Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) concerning government expenditure, government revenue, inflation, real effective exchange rate, and labour force participation rate. The R² value of 0.8785 indicates that about 88% of the variation in RGDP is explained by the model, while the adjusted R-squared of 0.7570 confirms strong explanatory power, though with some loss of degrees of freedom. The F-statistic of 7.23 (p = 0.0002) shows that the variables are jointly significant. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.12 suggests no

evidence of autocorrelation in the model. The coefficient of the error correction term CointEq1 is negative and highly significant (-0.4817, $p = 0.0000$), confirming that RGDP adjusts to correct disequilibrium from the long-run relationship at a speed of about 48% per period. Regarding short-run dynamics, past values of government expenditure at lag 1 and lag 2 have significant positive effects on RGDP, while government revenue at both lag 1 and lag 2 exerts significant negative effects. The real effective exchange rate at both lag 1 and lag 2 positively and significantly influences RGDP. The inflation rate at lag 1 and lag 2 shows significant negative effects, suggesting contractionary impacts of rising prices on RGDP. Labour force participation rate and past RGDP values appear not to exert significant short-run effects within the period studied. Overall, the results suggest that government expenditure, government revenue, exchange rate, and inflation rate are key drivers of short-run RGDP dynamics, while the significant error correction term confirms long-run equilibrium adjustment in the system.

Table 8: VECM Estimate with Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) as Dependent Variable (Nigeria)

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CointEq1	-0.481706	0.070741	-6.809439	0.0000
CointEq2	0.408505	0.063828	6.400128	0.0000
CointEq3	0.293631	0.062156	4.724099	0.0003
D(LOGGEXP(-1))	0.319938	0.048022	6.662354	0.0000
D(LOGGEXP(-2))	0.172997	0.031605	5.473659	0.0001
D(LOGGREV(-1))	-0.197686	0.056133	-3.521729	0.0031
D(LOGGREV(-2))	-0.065770	0.030188	-2.178674	0.0457
D(LOGLFPR(-1))	-0.249062	0.236319	-1.053925	0.3086
D(LOGLFPR(-2))	-0.383807	0.227099	-1.690040	0.1117
D(LOGREER(-1))	0.145088	0.031612	4.589608	0.0004
D(LOGREER(-2))	0.092394	0.025984	3.555856	0.0029
D(LOGRGDP(-1))	0.277717	0.195889	1.417728	0.1767
D(LOGRGDP(-2))	-0.196508	0.160010	-1.228096	0.2383
D(INFR(-1))	-0.006165	0.001319	-4.674158	0.0003
D(INFR(-2))	-0.004768	0.001446	-3.298093	0.0049
C	0.025989	0.006397	4.062523	0.0010
R-squared	0.878519	Mean dependent var		0.039698
Adjusted R-squared	0.757038	S.D. dependent var		0.036158
S.E. of regression	0.017823	Akaike info criterion		-4.910359
Sum squared resid	0.004765	Schwarz criterion		-4.170237
Log likelihood	92.11057	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.669098
F-statistic	7.231734	Durbin-Watson stat		2.123057
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000217			

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

1.2.1.1

Table 9 indicates the serial correlation LM test result for the VECM. The test examines whether the residuals of the model are serially correlated. The LM statistics at lag 1 (41.86, $p = 0.2316$), lag 2 (45.09, $p = 0.1424$), and lag 3 (29.01, $p = 0.7893$) are all statistically insignificant. This suggests that there is no evidence of serial correlation in the residuals of the model, indicating that the model is well specified in this regard. The probability values are based on the chi-square distribution with 36 degrees of freedom.

Diagnosis Tests

Table 9: Auto Serial Correlation Test

Lags	LM-Stat	Prob
------	---------	------

1	41.85511	0.2316
2	45.09104	0.1424
3	29.01106	0.7893

Probs from chi-square with 36 df.

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

To further examine the short-run causal relationships between the explanatory variables and real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria within the VECM, Table 11 presents the Granger causality test results. The findings reveal that government expenditure (Chi-sq = 35.08, $p = 0.0000$) and government revenue (Chi-sq = 19.27, $p = 0.0001$) both Granger-cause RGDP, suggesting that their past values significantly help predict changes in RGDP. Inflation (Chi-sq = 13.29, $p = 0.0013$) also Granger-causes RGDP at the 1% level of significance. However, labour force participation rate (Chi-sq = 2.75, $p = 0.2535$) and real effective exchange rate (Chi-sq = 3.58, $p = 0.1669$) do not show evidence of Granger causality for RGDP during the period studied. The joint test (Chi-sq = 121.56, $p = 0.0000$) confirms that the variables collectively have strong predictive power for RGDP dynamics. In summary, these results suggest that fiscal variables and inflation play a more significant role in explaining short-run variations in RGDP than labour force participation or exchange rate in Nigeria during the period examined.

Table 10: Granger Causality Test based on Vector Error Correction Model

Dependent variable: D(LOGRGDP)

Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
D(LOGGEXP)	35.08006	2	0.0000
D(LOGGREV)	19.27030	2	0.0001
D(LOGLFPR)	2.745112	2	0.2535
D(LOGREER)	3.580993	2	0.1669
D(INFR)	13.28539	2	0.0013
All	121.5616	10	0.0000

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

1.2.1.2

4.2.2 Impulse Response Function

To examine the response of real gross domestic product (RGDP) to fiscal policy and other macroeconomic shocks in Nigeria, the impulse response function (IRF) graphs are presented in Figure 4.1. The graphs illustrate how RGDP reacts over time to one standard deviation shocks in government expenditure (GEXP), government revenue (GREV), labour force participation rate (LFPR), real effective exchange rate (REER), and inflation rate (INFR). The results show that a positive shock to RGDP initially triggers an increase in government expenditure, but this effect quickly turns negative, displaying an unstable trend over time. In the case of government revenue, RGDP responds with an initial slight increase, followed by a sharp and significant rise around the third period before stabilising with smaller fluctuations after a notable decline at the fourth period. The shock of RGDP on LFPR results in relatively mild fluctuations, indicating a low standard deviation response. For REER, the response is steady, suggesting minimal volatility following the shock. Inflation (INFR) shows a positive initial reaction to an RGDP shock, but the response alternates between upward and downward movements while remaining on the positive side.

Fig 4.1: Impulse response of RGDP to key indicators in Nigeria. **Source:** Researchers' Computation, 2025.

4.2.3 Results for Libya

Table 11: Co-integration Test Result for Libya

Hypothesized	Trace Statistic				Maximum Eigenvalue Statistic			
	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistics	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.758	168.188	95.754	0.000	0.758	45.400	40.078	0.012
At most 1 *	0.716	122.790	69.819	0.000	0.716	40.274	33.877	0.008
At most 2 *	0.626	82.516	47.856	0.000	0.626	31.477	27.584	0.015
At most 3 *	0.620	51.039	29.797	0.000	0.620	30.922	21.132	0.002
At most 4	0.404	20.117	15.495	0.009	0.404	16.584	14.265	0.021
At most 5	0.105	3.533	3.841	0.060	0.105	3.533	3.841	0.060

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

Table 11 displays the results of the co-integration test conducted on Economic Growth, Monetary, and Fiscal Policy variables. The test statistics reject the null hypothesis of no co-integration among the variables, indicating the

presence of at least one co-integrating relationship. The existence of a single co-integrating equation is sufficient to confirm a long-run equilibrium relationship within the model. This justifies the application of the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) in the subsequent analysis.

Table 12: Lag Order of Selection

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-900.2287	NA	9.93e+17	58.46637	58.74392	58.55684
1	-657.5309	375.7903	1.68e+12	45.13102	47.07385*	45.76434
2	-611.3609	53.61676	1.16e+12	44.47490	48.08299	45.65105
3	-538.5497	56.36992*	2.59e+11	42.09998*	47.37335	43.81897*

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

Table 12 presents the lag order selection results for the variables used in this study. The lag length was evaluated up to a maximum of three. An asterisk (*) denotes the optimal lag selected by each information criterion. Based on the majority of selection criteria, specifically the LR test, Final prediction error (FPE), Akaike information criterion (AIC), and Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ), the optimal lag length is 3. However, the Schwarz information criterion (SC) criterion suggests lag 1. Given the overall support from multiple indicators, lag 3 is considered the appropriate lag length for the VAR model.

Similarly, the results in Appendix II (see the appendices section) presents the vector error correction estimates for Libya, which examined the relationship between RGDP, government expenditure, government revenue, labour force participation, real effective exchange rate and inflation. The results show that the error correction term for RGDP is negative and significant, confirming long-run equilibrium adjustment. In the short run, government expenditure, government revenue, and inflation significantly influence RGDP, while labour force participation and exchange rate show weaker effects. The model explains about 95% of the variation in RGDP, indicating strong overall fit.

Table 13: Vector Error Correction Model Estimates for Libya

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CointEq1	-0.769406	0.225777	-3.407818	0.0039
CointEq2	-0.005867	0.215293	-0.027252	0.9786
CointEq3	0.444635	0.191315	2.324105	0.0346
D(LOGGEXP(-1))	0.686725	0.166981	4.112604	0.0009
D(LOGGEXP(-2))	0.815613	0.142045	5.741923	0.0000
D(LOGGREV(-1))	-0.109113	0.174573	-0.625028	0.5413
D(LOGGREV(-2))	0.593062	0.167178	3.547491	0.0029
D(LOGLFPR(-1))	-1.201794	1.696203	-0.708520	0.4895
D(LOGLFPR(-2))	0.960025	1.609639	0.596422	0.5598
D(LOGREER(-1))	0.400395	0.235418	1.700785	0.1096
D(LOGREER(-2))	0.122997	0.124304	0.989489	0.3381
D(LOGRGDP(-1))	-0.793842	0.161281	-4.922090	0.0002
D(LOGRGDP(-2))	-0.787889	0.164838	-4.779784	0.0002
D(INFR(-1))	0.002361	0.004978	0.474283	0.6421
D(INFR(-2))	0.017233	0.005505	3.130261	0.0069
C	-0.136457	0.035182	-3.878590	0.0015
R-squared	0.950627	Mean dependent var		0.000185
Adjusted R-squared	0.901255	S.D. dependent var		0.211237
S.E. of regression	0.066379	Akaike info criterion		-2.280560
Sum squared resid	0.066092	Schwarz criterion		-1.540437
Log likelihood	51.34868	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.039298
F-statistic	19.25416	Durbin-Watson stat		2.504774

Prob(F-statistic) 0.000000

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

The highlighted column in Appendix II was therefore, interpreted and broken down in Table 13. The results in the Table reveal that the R^2 value of 0.951 shows that the explanatory variables explain about 95.1% of the variation in real GDP. Furthermore, the F-statistic of 19.254 ($P=0.000$) implies that the variables are jointly significant. The value (D.W. Statistics = 2.50) shows that the model is free from the autocorrelation problem. The negative but insignificance of the coefficient of error correction term (-0.7694) with real GDP as the dependent variable provides the evidence that the current real GDP of Libya failed to respond to disequilibrium from the past values of adjusted net national income (GREV), real GDP (RGDP), gross national expenditure (GEXP), inflation rate (INFR), labour force participation rate (LFPR), and real effective exchange rate (REER), during the period. In general; the result showed that, past values of gross national expenditure (GEXP), real effective exchange rate (REER), and inflation rate (INFR), are positively related to real GDP (RGDP), while adjusted net national income (GREV), and labour force participation rate (LFPR), are negatively related to real GDP (RGDP), with gross national expenditure (GEXP), and inflation rate (INFR) significant at 1%, implying that their past values affect the current values of the real GDP under study in Libya.

1.2.1.3 Diagnostic Tests

Table 14: Auto Serial Correlation Test

Lags	LM-Stat	Prob
1	32.55777	0.6331
2	36.87214	0.4284
3	31.87903	0.6650

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

The model is validated by applying Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test with the null hypothesis of no serial correlation at lag order. The results in Table 14 depict that we do not reject the null hypothesis, hence there is no serial correlation.

Table 15: Granger Causality based on the Vector Error Correction Model

Dependent variable: D(LOGRGDP)

Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
D(LOGGEXP)	35.08006	2	0.0000
D(LOGGREV)	19.27030	2	0.0001
D(LOGLFPR)	2.745112	2	0.2535
D(LOGREER)	3.580993	2	0.1669
D(INFR)	13.28539	2	0.0013
All	121.5616	10	0.0000

Source: Researchers' Computation using EViews, 2025.

To further investigate the short run causal relationship among the explanatory variable and Real GDP in the VECM model, Table 15 presents the result of the short-run causality between explanatory variables and Real GDP. From the result explanatory variables does Granger Cause Real GDP, implying that causality runs from GEXP, GREV, and INFR to real GDP, but it does not run through LFPR and REER to real GDP in Libya during the period of this study.

1.2.1.4 4.2.4 Impulse Response Function

The impulse response function graphs illustrate how Real GDP reacts to shocks in various explanatory variables. The diagrams in Figure 4.2 show a fluctuating response to gross national expenditure, suggesting varying sensitivity over time, while the real effective exchange rate has a relatively stable effect, moving GDP closer to zero. Adjusted net national income induces a positive response in period 2, whereas Labour Force Participation Rate triggers a negative shock in period 4, indicating an economic contraction. Similarly, the Inflation Rate leads to a positive shock in period 3, followed by fluctuations in subsequent periods.

Fig 4.2: Impulse response of RGDP to key indicators in Libya. **Source:** Researchers' Computation, 2025.

5. DISCUSSION

This section presents a comparative analysis of the VECM estimates for Nigeria and Libya, with a focus on the key determinants of real GDP (RGDP) dynamics in both countries. The analysis draws on short-run and long-run coefficients, adjustment parameters, and model diagnostics to evaluate economic relationships and model performance.

In the long run, both countries show some significant differences. These differences have implications for fiscal and macroeconomic policy in both countries. In Nigeria, government expenditure remains a key driver of economic growth, with both current and lagged spending showing strong and statistically significant positive effects on real GDP. However, unlike Libya, Nigeria shows negative and significant short-run effects of government revenue, suggesting that revenue collection may exert a contractionary effect, possibly due to inefficiencies in the tax system or burdensome tax practices. Inflation also plays a more prominent role in Nigeria, with both lags of inflation having negative and significant effects on output,

implying that price instability undermines growth. Additionally, the real effective exchange rate (REER) significantly supports GDP in Nigeria, suggesting a more active channel through which external competitiveness influences domestic output.

On the other hand, Libya's model suggests stronger long-run adjustment dynamics but a more expansionary impact of revenue and weaker inflationary constraints. These differences imply that Nigeria must focus on improving the efficiency of revenue use, controlling inflation, and leveraging exchange rate policies, while Libya should prioritize sustaining fiscal expansion and strengthening long-run macroeconomic stability mechanisms. However, both countries must commit to structural reforms to enhance the effectiveness of labour market participation, which remains insignificant in both contexts. The findings in both Nigeria and Libya support the findings in the works of Banjo et al., (2024) and Hakimah, (2025) who found that monetary policy had a negative impact and fiscal policy had a positive impact on economic growth in developing countries. It is imperative for both the Nigerian and Libyan governments to implement monetary and fiscal policy measures that best suit the individual economy, so that economic growth will be boosted.

6. CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The importance of monetary and fiscal policy instruments cannot be underestimated, as they unarguably play crucial roles in contributing to the growth of countries. For instance, expansionary monetary policy is used to increase the money supply in an economy. The effect of that is an increase in spending. Increased spending causes a rise in aggregate demand. An increase in aggregate demand will also increase aggregate supply, which will in turn increase aggregate investment, thereby increasing government revenue via an increase in revenue from taxation. When the Central Bank uses one or more of its tools to implement expansionary monetary policy to increase the money supply, the main effect is that people have more access to money. If people have more money, they have more reasons to spend money, increasing aggregate demand for goods and services. It is this increase in aggregate that helps stimulate the economy. From the findings of this study, it is important that the Nigerian and Libyan governments have to prioritize sustaining fiscal expansion and strengthening long-run macroeconomic stability mechanisms in order to boost economic growth.

6.1 RECOMMENDATIONS

Therefore, based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made.

With respect to Nigeria, first, the findings of this study showed that government expenditure had a significant positive effect on RGDP. This study, therefore, recommends that the Nigerian government should spend more money on projects that have economic benefits that will help to grow the economy. This can be done by looking at the needs of the six geopolitical zones in the country so that no zone will be short-changed. Second, the Nigerian government and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should make concerted efforts to reduce the present inflation in the country as the findings of this study revealed that inflation had a negative effect on economic growth. This can be done by embarking on contractionary monetary and fiscal policies, which will reduce the money supply and also, and the government needs to encourage the production of goods and services. Third, the Nigerian government should work on improving the welfare of the citizens in order to reduce the brain drain that is currently affecting the exodus of professionals in virtually all sectors of the Nigerian economy.

Concerning Libya, the findings of this study showed that government expenditure had a significant positive effect on RGDP. This study, therefore, recommends that the Libyan government should increase spending on projects with

economic benefits that will help to grow the economy. Furthermore, the Libyan government and the Central Bank in that country need to improve the value of the Libyan currency (the Dinar) relative to the US Dollar. Achieving this will support exports and reduce imports, thereby encouraging local production of goods and services. Lastly, the Libyan government should work to retain citizens by improving their welfare and remuneration. In summary, this study recommends that the Nigerian and Libyan governments should implement monetary and fiscal policy instruments that will help boost the economic growth of their respective countries.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

The major limitation that this study faced is the dearth of data. The researchers had wanted to use the time frame between 1980 and 2023, but because the data for 1980 to 1992 were not available, the study had to use the time frame used in this study. Coupled with this is the fact that the data for some variables were not available for countries such as South Africa, Tunisia, and Algeria, which the researchers wanted to include in the sample of countries. As regards suggestions for further studies, researchers wishing to embark on similar studies can do a cross-continental study that will compare the countries in the African continent with countries in Asia or Europe. This will bring out a better picture of how Africa is faring compared with other continents of the world and what lessons African countries can learn from the more developed countries of the world.

AUTHOR DECLARATION

The authors declared that no potential conflicts of interest with respect to research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS: Conceptualization, O.A., and O.A.M., methodology, O.A., formal analysis, O.A., writing – original draft preparation, O.A.M., writing – review and editing, O.A., and O.A.M. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

FUNDING: The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

References

- Amidu, M., Iddrisu, A.G., Andani, A. & Agyeman, B. (2022a). *Bank Pricing Behaviour, Monetary Policy and Inclusive Finance in Africa* (pp. 335–369). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-04162-4_10.
- Banjo, A., Iwayemi, A. & Oyedele, O. (2024). Natural resources and economic performance in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Finance and Management*, 159-179.
- Gaber, S., Gruevski, I. & Gaber, V. (2013). The effects of discretionary fiscal policy on macroeconomic aggregates. *BEH-Business and Economic Horizons*, 9(1), 33-40.
- Hakimah, Y. (2025). Monetary and fiscal policy: Drivers of stability in developing economies. *Jurnal Konseling dan Pendidikan*, 13(1), 1-10.
- Kabashi, R. (2017). Macroeconomic effects of fiscal policy in the European Union, with particular reference to transition countries. *Public Sector Economics*, 41(1), 39-69
- Kerner, P., Kalthaus, M. & Wendler, T. (2023). Economic growth and the use of natural resources: assessing the moderating role of institutions. *Energy Economics*, 126, 106942.

- Khan, S., Tariq, M. & Khan, M.A. (2025, February). Exploring the impact of monetary policy and institutional quality on inflation, investment, and economic growth in G-10 economies. In *Natural Resources Forum*. Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
- Matthew, A.O., Agidee, E.D., Adediran, O. & Osabohien, R. (2019). Technology-based FDI, manufacturing output and economic growth: A comparative analysis between Nigeria and Malaysia. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)*, 10(03), 470–487
- Muhammed Salik, A. & Oladipo, O. (2024). Effects of monetary policy on economic indicators in rural-urban Nigeria. In *Sci Set J of Economics Res*, 3(1), 67-88. www.mkscienceset.com.
- Ngaikedi, O.F., Ezu, G.K., Nwanna, I.O. & Ananwude, A. C. (2023a). Effect of Financial Inclusion on Monetary Policy Fundamentals in Nigeria (1986-2021). In *Int. J. adv. multidisc. Res. Stud*, 3(3), 45-65. www.multiresearchjournal.com.
- Njeze, F.I. (2023). Monetary policy transmission mechanisms and economic growth in Nigeria: An empirical investigation (1999-2021). *Global Journal of Finance and Business Review*, 6(3), 50. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8318625>.
- Obradović, L., & Grubišić, Z. (2025). The impact of monetary policy on economic growth in SEE countries: A Multivariate Approach. *Journal of Central Banking Theory and Practice*, 2, 91-119.
- Olapade, O.V. (2025). Monetary policy, institutional quality and inclusive growth in Nigeria. An unpublished Ph.D Thesis submitted to the Department of Economics and Development Studies, Covenant University, Ota.
- Olawale, H. (2024). The impact of monetary policies on the economic growth of Nigeria. *International Journal of Financial Research and Business Development*, 4(7), 23-39.
- Pastpipatkul, P. & Ko, H. (2025). The efficacy of monetary and fiscal policies on economic growth: Evidence from Thailand. *Economies*, 13(1), 19-37.
- Saheb, T., Sidaoui, M. & Schmarzo, B. (2024). Convergence of artificial intelligence with social media: A bibliometric and qualitative analysis. *Telematics and Informatics Reports*, 14, 100146.
- Şahin, A. (2025). The role of monetary and fiscal policies in ensuring financial stability. *Optimum Ekonomi ve Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 12(1), 25-46.
- Tajudeen, E. & Adesina, A. M. (2024). Financial economics effect of monetary policy and financial development on foreign direct investment inflow in Nigeria. *AUDOE*, 20(2), 109–122.
- Tan, C.T., Mohamed, A., Habibullah, M.S. & Chin, L. (2020). The impacts of monetary and fiscal policies on economic growth in Malaysia, Singapore and Thailand. *South Asian Journal of Macroeconomics and Public Finance*, 9(1), 114-130.
- Utouh, H.M. & Kitole, F.A. (2025). The impact of fiscal and monetary policy on economic growth and structural transformation in Tanzania. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 13(1), 2499013. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2025.2499013>.
- World Bank, (2024). Global Economic Prospects, June 2024. World Bank Publications.

APPENDICES

Appendix I: Vector Error Correction Estimates (Nigeria)

Error Correction:	D(LOGGEXP)	D(LOGGREV)	D(LOGLFPR)	D(LOGREER)	D(LOGRGDP)	D(INFR)
CointEq1	-0.490706	-1.966508	0.092784	-0.669408	-0.481706	46.34797

	(0.53156) [-0.92315]	(0.33179) [-5.92693]	(0.08036) [1.15462]	(0.36665) [-1.82575]	(0.07074) [-6.80944]	(14.5079) [3.19467]
CointEq2	0.944139 (0.47961) [1.96856]	1.604714 (0.29937) [5.36036]	-0.082412 (0.07251) [-1.13663]	0.946242 (0.33082) [2.86032]	0.408505 (0.06383) [6.40013]	-14.12553 (13.0901) [-1.07910]
CointEq3	-2.508470 (0.46705) [-5.37089]	1.719749 (0.29153) [5.89910]	-0.103799 (0.07061) [-1.47010]	0.555532 (0.32215) [1.72443]	0.293631 (0.06216) [4.72410]	-101.8782 (12.7473) [-7.99214]
D(LOGGEXP(-1))	-0.068501 (0.36084) [-0.18984]	1.654847 (0.22523) [7.34724]	-0.056325 (0.05455) [-1.03252]	0.540561 (0.24890) [2.17183]	0.319938 (0.04802) [6.66235]	-24.66015 (9.84856) [-2.50393]
D(LOGGEXP(-2))	0.151057 (0.23749) [0.63606]	0.969802 (0.14824) [6.54224]	-0.045684 (0.03590) [-1.27245]	0.037447 (0.16381) [0.22860]	0.172997 (0.03161) [5.47366]	-5.805863 (6.48180) [-0.89572]
D(LOGGREV(-1))	-0.852207 (0.42179) [-2.02044]	-1.203840 (0.26328) [-4.57249]	0.077617 (0.06377) [1.21723]	-0.601035 (0.29094) [-2.06585]	-0.197686 (0.05613) [-3.52173]	-5.205290 (11.5121) [-0.45216]
D(LOGGREV(-2))	-1.250953 (0.22684) [-5.51473]	-0.346917 (0.14159) [-2.45016]	0.052746 (0.03429) [1.53809]	-0.105174 (0.15646) [-0.67219]	-0.065770 (0.03019) [-2.17867]	-27.54693 (6.19115) [-4.44940]
D(LOGLFPR(-1))	2.141661 (1.77573) [1.20607]	-1.122114 (1.10839) [-1.01238]	0.665818 (0.26845) [2.48023]	0.095912 (1.22484) [0.07831]	-0.249062 (0.23632) [-1.05392]	147.6671 (48.4655) [3.04685]
D(LOGLFPR(-2))	2.224589 (1.70646) [1.30363]	-1.419703 (1.06515) [-1.33286]	0.430534 (0.25798) [1.66888]	-0.150666 (1.17705) [-0.12800]	-0.383807 (0.22710) [-1.69004]	27.23064 (46.5747) [0.58467]
D(LOGREER(-1))	0.681961 (0.23754) [2.87095]	0.708519 (0.14827) [4.77860]	-0.018330 (0.03591) [-0.51045]	0.213673 (0.16385) [1.30411]	0.145088 (0.03161) [4.58961]	2.428178 (6.48320) [0.37453]
D(LOGREER(-2))	0.343819 (0.19525) [1.76096]	0.358906 (0.12187) [2.94499]	-0.004730 (0.02952) [-0.16024]	0.035917 (0.13467) [0.26669]	0.092394 (0.02598) [3.55586]	-1.657352 (5.32887) [-0.31101]
D(LOGRGDP(-1))	-0.981731 (1.47194) [-0.66697]	0.008095 (0.91877) [0.00881]	-0.239746 (0.22252) [-1.07740]	0.307651 (1.01529) [0.30302]	0.277717 (0.19589) [1.41773]	32.96529 (40.1739) [0.82056]
D(LOGRGDP(-2))	2.864024 (1.20234) [2.38204]	-0.285388 (0.75049) [-0.38027]	0.144226 (0.18177) [0.79347]	-1.365865 (0.82933) [-1.64695]	-0.196508 (0.16001) [-1.22810]	31.39594 (32.8158) [0.95673]
D(INFR(-1))	-0.009819 (0.00991) [-0.99070]	-0.044156 (0.00619) [-7.13771]	0.002635 (0.00150) [1.75893]	-0.034050 (0.00684) [-4.98081]	-0.006165 (0.00132) [-4.67416]	0.010017 (0.27050) [0.03703]
D(INFR(-2))	0.004167 (0.01086) [0.38360]	-0.021264 (0.00678) [-3.13603]	0.002371 (0.00164) [1.44364]	-0.015321 (0.00749) [-2.04470]	-0.004768 (0.00145) [-3.29809]	-0.179022 (0.29649) [-0.60381]
C	0.105331 (0.04807)	0.045651 (0.03000)	-0.003645 (0.00727)	0.092999 (0.03316)	0.025989 (0.00640)	0.946269 (1.31198)

	[2.19120]	[1.52147]	[-0.50158]	[2.80483]	[4.06252]	[0.72125]
R-squared	0.949053	0.906688	0.785831	0.952902	0.878519	0.937625
Adj. R-squared	0.898106	0.813375	0.571661	0.905804	0.757038	0.875251
Sum sq. resids	0.269030	0.104817	0.006149	0.127997	0.004765	200.4057
S.E. equation	0.133923	0.083593	0.020246	0.092375	0.017823	3.655186
F-statistic	18.62816	9.716706	3.669199	20.23222	7.231734	15.03219
Log likelihood	29.59017	44.20054	88.15857	41.10377	92.11057	-72.91563
Akaike AIC	-0.876785	-1.819390	-4.655392	-1.619598	-4.910359	5.736492
Schwarz SC	-0.136663	-1.079267	-3.915269	-0.879476	-4.170237	6.476614
Mean dependent	0.054489	0.074471	-0.003080	0.027185	0.039698	-0.642880
S.D. dependent	0.419546	0.193502	0.030935	0.300980	0.036158	10.34882
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)		1.82E-13				
Determinant resid covariance		2.34E-15				
Log likelihood		258.2827				
Akaike information criterion		-9.115014				
Schwarz criterion		-3.702869				

Appendix II: Vector Error Correction Estimates (Libya)

Vector Error Correction Estimates

Date: 06/17/25 Time: 13:40

Sample (adjusted): 1993 2023

Included observations: 31 after adjustments

Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []

Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1	CointEq2	CointEq3			
LOGGEXP(-1)	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000			
LOGGREV(-1)	0.000000	1.000000	0.000000			
LOGLFPR(-1)	0.000000	0.000000	1.000000			
LOGREER(-1)	1.102215 (0.56666) [1.94509]	2.171561 (0.48235) [4.50204]	0.394103 (0.33129) [1.18959]			
LOGRGDP(-1)	0.349118 (0.17159) [2.03463]	0.362518 (0.14606) [2.48202]	0.028732 (0.10032) [0.28641]			
INFR(-1)	-0.004091 (0.00371) [-1.10247]	-0.031139 (0.00316) [-9.85819]	0.013877 (0.00217) [6.39655]			
@TREND(90)	-0.096742 (0.01167) [-8.28644]	-0.025956 (0.00994) [-2.61186]	-0.045311 (0.00683) [-6.63845]			
C	-8.432147	-14.57609	-5.452079			
Error Correction:	D(LOGGEXP)	D(LOGGREV)	D(LOGLFPR)	D(LOGREER)	D(LOGRGDP)	D(INFR)
CointEq1	-1.377338 (0.43400) [-3.17359]	0.944618 (0.44539) [2.12087]	0.010298 (0.03962) [0.25995]	0.202717 (0.13736) [1.47576]	-0.769406 (0.22578) [-3.40782]	9.382706 (21.9813) [0.42685]

CointEq2	0.658854 (0.41385) [1.59203]	-1.290742 (0.42471) [-3.03912]	0.018059 (0.03778) [0.47806]	-0.214192 (0.13099) [-1.63523]	-0.005867 (0.21529) [-0.02725]	8.614042 (20.9606) [0.41096]
CointEq3	-0.409523 (0.36775) [-1.11358]	0.134683 (0.37741) [0.35687]	0.077636 (0.03357) [2.31277]	-0.338917 (0.11640) [-2.91172]	0.444635 (0.19131) [2.32411]	4.793285 (18.6261) [0.25734]
D(LOGGEXP(-1))	0.573788 (0.32098) [1.78762]	0.020889 (0.32940) [0.06341]	-0.006913 (0.02930) [-0.23595]	-0.155135 (0.10159) [-1.52703]	0.686725 (0.16698) [4.11260]	5.178368 (16.2570) [0.31853]
D(LOGGEXP(-2))	0.720295 (0.27305) [2.63799]	0.220673 (0.28021) [0.78752]	-0.017874 (0.02492) [-0.71716]	-0.065359 (0.08642) [-0.75628]	0.815613 (0.14205) [5.74192]	-2.910686 (13.8293) [-0.21047]
D(LOGGREV(-1))	-0.257392 (0.33557) [-0.76702]	0.769367 (0.34438) [2.23406]	0.016624 (0.03063) [0.54273]	0.085622 (0.10621) [0.80614]	-0.109113 (0.17457) [-0.62503]	-8.754711 (16.9962) [-0.51510]
D(LOGGREV(-2))	0.100785 (0.32136) [0.31362]	1.178887 (0.32979) [3.57463]	-0.014513 (0.02933) [-0.49474]	0.047233 (0.10171) [0.46437]	0.593062 (0.16718) [3.54749]	-10.95801 (16.2762) [-0.67326]
D(LOGLFPR(-1))	5.380507 (3.26053) [1.65020]	-0.023232 (3.34611) [-0.00694]	-0.390190 (0.29762) [-1.31103]	2.166527 (1.03199) [2.09937]	-1.201794 (1.69620) [-0.70852]	-146.4265 (165.140) [-0.88668]
D(LOGLFPR(-2))	5.178909 (3.09413) [1.67379]	1.503505 (3.17534) [0.47349]	0.041054 (0.28243) [0.14536]	2.422825 (0.97932) [2.47399]	0.960025 (1.60964) [0.59642]	-58.06032 (156.712) [-0.37049]
D(LOGREER(-1))	0.106668 (0.45253) [0.23571]	0.533041 (0.46441) [1.14778]	-0.085579 (0.04131) [-2.07178]	0.039908 (0.14323) [0.27863]	0.400395 (0.23542) [1.70078]	-19.83361 (22.9199) [-0.86534]
D(LOGREER(-2))	-0.115676 (0.23894) [-0.48411]	0.199615 (0.24522) [0.81404]	-0.055576 (0.02181) [-2.54811]	-0.405064 (0.07563) [-5.35601]	0.122997 (0.12430) [0.98949]	-11.68362 (12.1021) [-0.96542]
D(LOGRGDP(-1))	0.135320 (0.31002) [0.43648]	-0.535191 (0.31816) [-1.68214]	-0.023233 (0.02830) [-0.82099]	0.172927 (0.09813) [1.76231]	-0.793842 (0.16128) [-4.92209]	-0.696715 (15.7021) [-0.04437]
D(LOGRGDP(-2))	-0.044465 (0.31686) [-0.14033]	-1.018354 (0.32518) [-3.13170]	0.008305 (0.02892) [0.28716]	0.088852 (0.10029) [0.88595]	-0.787889 (0.16484) [-4.77978]	-3.335518 (16.0484) [-0.20784]
D(INFR(-1))	0.028345 (0.00957) [2.96217]	-0.016030 (0.00982) [-1.63238]	-0.000295 (0.00087) [-0.33752]	0.002708 (0.00303) [0.89414]	0.002361 (0.00498) [0.47428]	0.318685 (0.48465) [0.65755]
D(INFR(-2))	0.020282 (0.01058) [1.91647]	-0.016549 (0.01086) [-1.52373]	3.42E-05 (0.00097) [0.03539]	-0.001492 (0.00335) [-0.44557]	0.017233 (0.00551) [3.13026]	-0.404932 (0.53600) [-0.75547]
C	-0.127507 (0.06763) [-1.88539]	-0.056977 (0.06940) [-0.82094]	0.009466 (0.00617) [1.53349]	-0.054599 (0.02141) [-2.55073]	-0.136457 (0.03518) [-3.87859]	1.551199 (3.42528) [0.45287]

R-squared	0.711733	0.764606	0.922156	0.819356	0.950627	0.513403
Adj. R-squared	0.423466	0.529213	0.844313	0.638711	0.901255	0.026807
Sum sq. resids	0.244213	0.257201	0.002035	0.024465	0.066092	626.4640
S.E. equation	0.127596	0.130946	0.011647	0.040385	0.066379	6.462528
F-statistic	2.469004	3.248204	11.84629	4.535738	19.25416	1.055090
Log likelihood	31.09028	30.28710	105.2989	66.75276	51.34868	-90.58171
Akaike AIC	-0.973567	-0.921749	-5.761216	-3.274371	-2.280560	6.876239
Schwarz SC	-0.233444	-0.181626	-5.021094	-2.534249	-1.540437	7.616362
Mean dependent	0.096937	0.017458	0.006887	-0.009068	0.000185	-0.225373
S.D. dependent	0.168045	0.190844	0.029518	0.067189	0.211237	6.550929
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)		3.58E-13				
Determinant resid covariance		4.60E-15				
Log likelihood		247.7875				
Akaike information criterion		-8.437904				
Schwarz criterion		-3.025758				

ICASuD 2025 CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS